

APPLICATION OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING HISTORY IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract. *A feature of the educational process with the use of computer tools is that the center of activity becomes the student, who, based on his individual abilities and interests, builds the process of cognition. A “subject-subjective” relationship develops between the teacher and the student. The teacher often acts as an assistant, consultant, encouraging original discoveries, stimulating activity, initiative and independence.*

Keywords: *innovative, method, ability, organizational form, natural subjects.*

At the present stage of development of secondary vocational education, the problem of training graduates with a good command of computer technologies acquires particular importance, due to the high pace of development and improvement of science and technology, the need south of society in people who are able to quickly navigate the environment, who are able to think independently and are free from stereotypes. The use of innovative technologies in teaching physics is also explained by the need to solve the problem of finding ways and means of activating the cognitive interest of students, developing their creative abilities, and stimulating their mental activity. A feature of the educational process with the use of computer tools is that the center of activity becomes the student, who, based on his individual abilities and interests, builds the process of cognition. A “subject-subjective” relationship develops between the teacher and the student. The teacher often acts as an assistant, consultant, encouraging original discoveries, stimulating activity, initiative and independence.

The learning process turns into a teaching/learning process. The development of physics education has exposed a number of serious contradictions that have a negative impact on the qualitative level of mastery of physical laws. These are contradictions:

- between the constantly growing volume of information and insufficient flexibility of curricula and plans;
- between the requirements of society for the level of development, subject training of students and the lack of real conditions for their implementation; between the need for personal and mental development of the student and the conditions for improving the health of children;
- between the wonderful idea of humanizing education and its rapid implementation in the form of reducing hours in natural subjects,
- between the need to build learning on the basis of the student’s creative activity, on the basis of an orientation “towards personal success” and the reproductive nature of learning,
- between the individual personal interests of the student, often determined by his cognitive capabilities, and existing organizational forms of education, focused on the work of the teacher with the group

Obviously, the use of innovative technologies is becoming relevant in the pedagogical process, which forms in students the skills of independently acquiring new knowledge, collecting and analyzing the necessary information, the ability to put forward hypotheses, draw conclusions

and draw conclusions. These technologies involve fundamentally new ways and methods of interaction between teachers and students, ensuring the effective achievement of the results of teaching activities and are based on a system-activity approach, implement developmental learning, and exclude ineffective verbal methods of knowledge transfer. motivate interactions between teacher and students, guaranteeing educational results. Based on all that has been said, I have set myself the following goal: to increase the success of learning in the subject by creating conditions for the formation of positive motivation for learning using innovative technologies when teaching physics.

To achieve the goal, I set myself the following tasks: to become familiar with the theoretical basis of innovative teaching technologies; use methods and techniques for the practical application of technologies; create diagnostic material for researching the effectiveness of technology use.

In teaching history, ICT technologies can be used at all stages of the lesson - to explain, reinforce, repeat, control new material. We will touch on some of them: *1) Explanation of new material.*

At this stage of the lesson, the most effective type of activity is educational. The impact of the educational material on the students depends to a large extent on the level of illustrativeness of the oral material. The visual richness of the educational material makes it vivid, reliable and promotes better learning and understanding.

When learning new material, the teacher can conduct a lecture using computer presentations, which allows students to focus on the important points of the presented information. The explanation of the lesson topic is accompanied by a slide presentation of the lesson topic and a lesson plan for the topic. Then the topic is explained according to the plan, students make the necessary abstracts. After explaining the topic, students solve oral exercises, and then solve more complex problems in their notebooks. All proposed tasks are also presented in slides.

A distinctive feature of using computer presentations is automatic management and limiting the time of presentation of slide shows, which allows students to focus their visual attention on particularly important moments of the educational material.

2) Problem solving.

At this stage of the lesson, the teaching type of activity is carried out. Various programs are being developed, their purpose is to teach students to solve problems, to analyze realities, because past realities and important dates are an integral part of studying history. Programs can include tasks of different levels of complexity, as well as historical puzzles, historical references aimed at logical thinking. Answers to these can be entered in years, dates, and in general form. In the second case, the reader enters the answers to the logic puzzle into the computer using the keyboard, and the program recognizes the answers regardless of how they are written.

3) Knowledge control.

Tests are used during monitoring (differentiation is possible). There are two possible forms of organization of tests, which can be called "choose the correct answer from the presented options" or "write the correct answer".

Organization of the test based on the principle of "choose the correct answer from the offered options" ensures the speed of passing the test, because it does not require special computer skills from students. He selects it from the options offered for answering and presses the button showing the correct answer number.

Organizing a test based on the principle of "Write the correct answer" assumes the student's initial good preparation as a personal computer user. The answer is given by typing it and requires good knowledge of the keyboard, including the ability to "switch to English" and write puzzle answers using special programs.

Also, in our classes, we can use the following interactive forms of teaching and supervision using ICT: creation of presentations by the teacher and students, computer modeling, virtual laboratory and practical work.

The experience of using programmed control of students' knowledge, especially using computer technologies, made it possible to distinguish the following positive aspects in the examination of knowledge in history:

- the possibility of tipping and cheating is eliminated; objectivity of knowledge assessment increases; the cognitive activity of students in studying history increases sharply, which is related to the stimulation of independent work according to this methodology; the role of the teacher changes, freed from the "punishment" functions related to knowledge control and assessment;
- the psychological environment among students improves;
- stable feedback is formed - teacher - student - teacher; using statistical data, the teacher can quickly get an objective picture of the educational activity, determine which aspects of the subject the students have learned the worst, and quickly adjust the educational process; the number of control events increases, which allows to test the knowledge of all groups of students on most sections of the studied subject in time; the student always considers this assessment to be objective, and the teacher always has information about the level of mastery of the material in the lesson.

In addition, using computer technologies, the teacher can create various educational and demonstration programs, models and games. Such effective developments form a positive attitude of students towards learning, offer an optimal method of support and increase the speed of individual learning for students.

The computer in the classroom is a tool that allows students to better know themselves, the individual characteristics of learning, how the meaning of an expression changes when one or another parameter changes, it helps to develop the independence of a certain operation.

Experience shows that the use of computer technologies in the teaching of history makes it possible to differentiate learning activities in the classroom, activates the students' interest in learning, develops their creative abilities, increases mental activity, and stimulates research results.

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